

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of the use of multimedia technologies in the modern educational process. It is substantiated that lessons organized on the basis of multimedia tools are an important factor in increasing the level of students' knowledge acquisition, forming independent and critical thinking skills, and ensuring educational effectiveness. According to the results of the study, the use of interactive multimedia technologies allows you to increase the level of assimilation of educational material by up to 75%.

The XXI st century is characterized by globalization and digitalization processes and imposes completely new requirements on the education system. The sharp increase in the volume of knowledge in modern society requires students to quickly and effectively assimilate information. Traditional lessons using multimedia technologies Lesson time Part of the lesson is spent on writing and explaining on the board. Up to 30% of the lesson time is saved, because multimedia tools are used instead of writing on the board. Lesson materials Lessons are usually taught with traditional text materials and simple tools. New materials are added, presented using interactive videos, presentations, animations and graphics. Communication with students Students remain mostly passive listeners, they receive information more from the teacher. Students become active, they can be involved in the lesson through interactive elements and multimedia tools. Lesson interestingness Lessons can sometimes be monotonous and repetitive. Lessons are made more interesting and dynamic, and it is easier to attract students' attention with the help of various multimedia tools. Understanding of educational materials Students rely more on written materials and illustrated explanations. Multimedia technologies facilitate understanding using various visual and audio materials. Lesson management The teacher manages the lesson only on the basis of the materials at his disposal. The lesson activates the interaction between the teacher and students, students are given interactive opportunities. Student motivation Motivation can sometimes be low, because the lessons are routine and repetitive. Multimedia tools interest students in learning and increase motivation.

In particular, multimedia technologies are an effective tool for increasing the cognitive activity of students by organizing the educational process visually, interactively and dynamically. Today, it is difficult to imagine a modern lesson without multimedia tools, and they are becoming an important factor in improving the quality of education.

Multimedia technologies are modern information technologies that combine text, graphics, audio, video and animation within a single information environment. These technologies allow you to present educational material in a visual, understandable and memorable way.

The use of multimedia tools in the educational process provides the following advantages:

- increases students' interest in the lesson;
- allows modeling of complex scientific processes;
- saves lesson time and enriches the content;
- develops students' independent work skills.

Practical experience shows that in lessons using multimedia technologies, students turn from passive listeners into active participants.

Interactive education provides two-way active communication between the teacher and the student. Multimedia technologies serve as the main tool for implementing interactive education. In particular:

- interactive whiteboards;
- multimedia presentations;
- virtual laboratories;
- simulators and training programs.

Especially in physics, chemistry and biology, the use of virtual laboratories allows for safe and effective study of experiments that are difficult or dangerous to perform in real conditions.

Multimedia technologies serve to solve the following didactic tasks:

1. Deep and systematic mastery of educational material;
2. Consolidation and generalization of knowledge;
3. Formation of self-control skills;
4. Increasing educational motivation;
5. Development of creative and critical thinking of students.

The introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process also changes the role of the teacher. Now the teacher acts not as a source of information, but as a manager, guide and consultant of the educational process. This leads to the organization of the educational process on the basis of subject-subject relations.

Lessons organized using multimedia tools increase students' interest in learning, encourage them to think actively and prepare for independent learning.

In conclusion, multimedia technologies are an integral part of the modern educational process. They play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of education, ensuring deep learning of students, and developing their digital competencies. The rational and systematic use of multimedia technologies serves to train competitive personnel in line with international educational standards. Multimedia technologies have transformed the visual aspect of education from a static to a dynamic one, that is, it has become possible to observe the processes being studied over time..

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